

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF FLUORONIOMATES OF ORGANIC BASE CATIONS

Compound	Found			Required		
	%N	%Nb	%F	%N	%Nb	%F
(Pyridine H) (NbOF ₄), C ₅ H ₅ NH(NbOF ₄)	5.41	34.9	29.0	5.28	35.1	28.7
(α -picoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₆ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.90	33.3	26.8	5.03	33.3	27.2
(β -picoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₆ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.89	33.4	27.4	5.03	33.3	27.2
(δ -picoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₆ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.72	33.6	27.1	5.03	33.3	27.2
(Quinoline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₉ H ₇ NH(NbOF ₄)	4.63	39.9	24.4	4.44	29.5	24.1
(<i>o</i> -phenanthroline H) (NbOF ₄), C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ H(NbOF ₄)	7.29	25.6	20.7	7.65	25.4	20.8
(Guanidine H ₂) (NbOF ₅), CH ₅ N ₃ H ₂ (NbOF ₅)	16.4	35.7	36.4	15.9	35.1	35.9
(Nitron H) (NbF ₆), C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ H(NbF ₆)	10.8	17.8	21.7	10.8	17.9	21.9
(α, α' -dipyridyl H ₂) (NbF ₆) ₂ , C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ H ₂ (NbF ₆) ₂	—	32.6	39.3	—	32.5	39.9

The compounds containing NbOF₄ group are well-crystalline, white, nonhygroscopic solids. The salts obtained from pyridine, quinoline and orthophenanthroline are highly soluble in water, whilst the solubility of picoline compound decreases according to the series $\alpha > \beta > \delta$. All the compounds are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. Guanidinium and dipyridyl salts are highly soluble in water, whereas nitron salt is sparingly soluble and hydrolyses on boiling. The nitron salt is soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, dioxan, etc.

It has been found that all the compounds except those of nitron and dipyridyl decompose without melting. The melting point of the nitron compound is 194° and that of dipyridyl compound above 300°.

Thermogravimetric studies: All the fluoroniomates are studied by thermogravimetry in a manually operated thermobalance at the heating rate of 2°C/min. Only in the case of dipyridyl compound an intermediate compound is formed in the temperature range 260°–350°, but it is so unstable that it cannot be isolated by isothermal heating of the compound at 240° to 250°. Maximum decomposition of the compounds takes place in the range 200°–300°, and near about 500° Nb₂O₅ is produced from them.

Infrared spectral studies: All the compounds have been studied through infrared spectroscopy in the region 700 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹. Pyridine, α -, β -, δ -picolines, quinoline and orthophenanthroline compounds show broad strong absorption bands due to Nb-O⁵ in the regions 780 cm⁻¹–845 cm⁻¹, 785 cm⁻¹–839 cm⁻¹, 780 cm⁻¹–800 cm⁻¹, 798 cm⁻¹–826 cm⁻¹, 790 cm⁻¹–820 cm⁻¹ and 787 cm⁻¹–810 cm⁻¹ respectively. Besides, known expected bands corresponding to these compounds are also found to occur. The above band due to Nb-O is absent in the nitron salt, but the dipyridyl compound shows a strong band in the region 797 cm⁻¹–835 cm⁻¹, which is also found in dipyridyl itself.

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Kinetics of Cr (VI) Oxidation of 1-and 2-Acetylnaphthalene

N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3

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ALTHOUGH chromic acid has been used as a versatile oxidant for the last two decades¹, the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of ketones, is of very recent origin. Best and Littler² have studied the kinetics of the oxidation of cyclohexanone by chromic acid. Rocek and Reihl³ have reported that aliphatic ketones are oxidised via their enol form. Bakore and coworkers⁴ have studied the kinetics and mechanism of chromic acid oxidation of some aliphatic ketones. Very recently we have reported the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some aromatic ketones⁵. The present paper deals with the kinetics of the oxidation of some ketones of the naphthalene series.

The ketones, 1-acetylnaphthalene and 2-acetylnaphthalene were prepared and purified according to the literature method⁶. The kinetics of these oxidations were studied in 90% HOAC—10% H₂O (vol/vol) in the presence of perchloric acid and at constant ionic strength. The method of rate measurement is similar to our previous method⁵.

The rate of disappearance of Cr (VI) followed first order rate law, but the values of rate constants decreased with increase in [Cr (VI)]. The reaction is also first order with respect to the [Ketone]. Under the conditions of constant ionic strength the first order rate constant k_1 is proportional to [H⁺].

The reaction has been studied in various acetic acid-water binary mixtures. Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increases the rate of oxidation. This is probably due to the lowering of dielectric constant of the medium, which favours reactions involving protonation⁷. The rate of the reaction decreases in the presence of added Mn (II) ions. The same retardation of reaction rate has been

